

"Pedagogical system of forming the culture of loyalty to the motherland of students and youth of Karakalpak"

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Annotation The methods of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism are aimed at forming the necessary knowledge, skills, skills and strong will, high spiritual and moral qualities in young people, and consist of factors that affect their mind, spirit and activity.

Key words: Youth, patriotic spirit, education, military discipline.

Young people differ from other socio-demographic groups by their special characteristics: they constantly change places of residence and jobs, take up new professions and try themselves in different fields.

Family separations and various negative situations, such as crime, alcoholism, and drug addiction, are much more common among members of this age group than among other age groups. In order to protect them from these harmful effects and to find their rightful place in life, almost all countries have a separate state policy for youth.

People with ulterior motives masterfully use these peculiarities and inexperience of them. If we pay attention to the revolutionary changes that have taken place in any

society and country, especially the disturbances that have been carried out from outside for the geopolitical goals of other countries, we can see that they are mainly done by the hands of the youth. Unfortunately, in the riots that occurred in Karakalpakstan on July 1-2, 2022, an attempt was made to use mostly young people.

Young people from Karakalpakstan have always been distinguished by their extraordinary talents. Talents such as Jenisbek Piyazov, who are surprising art lovers not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the world, did not come out of this country in vain.

Therefore, on the initiative of Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a youth festival was organized in Bozatov to introduce Karakalpak culture to the whole republic. More than 238,000 young people took part in the "Bozatov FEST" competition, which was held as part of the "Youth Month" in 2022, and at the final stage held in the Bozatov district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, four representatives of the city of Karakalpakstan and Tashkent, Young people from Tashkent region won 2, Surkhandarya and Jizzakh regions won 1 each. In the republic stage, the winners and prize-winners received 50 million soums for the 1st place, 30 million soums for the 2nd place, and 20 million soums for the 3rd place.

The Karakalpaks are a creative people, and they have been participating equally in the work being done in this regard in our country. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his speech at the Dzhokorgi Council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, made a special mention of this: "In the last five years, the volume of construction works has increased 3.5 times. Dozens of new production facilities, modern agroclusters, and joint ventures have been put into operation. Thousands of new objects were built, reconstructed and repaired in the republic. In particular, many kindergartens, general and specialized schools,

universities, healthcare, scientific, cultural and sports facilities have been commissioned. "The level of coverage of children of kindergarten age with pre-school education has reached 75 percent from 32 percent in 2017," he said.

According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 209 dated April 13, 2021, the money spent on education is paid from the fund of the Youth Affairs Agency to young people who have obtained a high score (level) through international examination systems. Young people from Karakalpakstan actively participated in this process, and 219.2 million soums were paid to 121 of them through the Department of the Youth Affairs Agency of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

All these processes are being done for the future of Karakalpakstan, for the youth of Karakalpakstan. I think that the true patriotic youth of Karakalpakstan will continue to win on sports fields, on world stages, and in science Olympiads. We know the Karakalpak people as a creative people, and it is these young men and women who show the whole world that the Karakalpaks today, like their ancestors, are a creative, creative, talented people.

The system of educating young people in the military-patriotic spirit is a continuous process, which consists of a complex of interrelated political-legal, socio-economic, ideological-ideological, cultural-educational activities. In my experience, one determined, enterprising, alert, battle-hardened, brave, and enthusiastic person is better than a thousand inactive and indifferent people. Because one experienced person orders thousands of people.

Education of young people in the military-patriotic spirit is carried out in accordance with the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees, decisions and orders of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions and orders of

the Cabinet of Ministers and other legal documents. Education of young people in the spirit of patriotism is regularly organized on a systematic and scientific basis. "The military potential of the country is determined by modern weapons and military equipment, brave soldiers and officers, their physical and moral training. In this sense, the true strength of our national army is, first of all, you - passionate and selfless people who dedicate their lives to the sacred work of protecting the Motherland, - said Shavkat Mirziyoyev. pre-school education, general secondary education, vocational education and higher educational institutions aimed at forming and developing moral values, love and loyalty to the Motherland; state and non-state non-profit organizations, as well as other organizations, that carry out mass patriotic work. The following are the main principles of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism: scientificity, historicity, accuracy and promptness, regularity, activity, harmony of education and training work, consistency of the educational process, reliance on positive results and achievements in patriotic education. The following are methods of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism:

- persuasion, training and independent work;
- observation, encouragement, example and personal example.

At the heart of all our reforms is the noble goal of "appreciating the human being," said the President. - First of all, this means ensuring the family of each citizen, the peace of the neighborhood, the peace of the country. To appreciate a person, first of all, our sky should be clear, our borders should be inviolable, and our borders should be strong. Today you are fulfilling such a task with honor. Indeed, educating young people in the spirit of loyalty to the motherland is our most important task, and educating young people in the spirit of patriotism is organized in various forms, including scientific-practical conferences, question-and-answer evenings, readings, games, meetings with famous people, and other forms. They provide a variety of

spiritual and educational work, ultimately serve to create a healthy social and spiritual environment in the society.

The state is the main institution that ensures the organization of the system of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism and the monitoring of its results. The state supports the education process of the young generation in the family, preschool education, general secondary education, vocational education and higher education institutions, during military service, as well as self-government bodies of citizens, various organizes within the framework of state and non-state non-profit organizations. Education of young people in the spirit of patriotism is carried out in the following four stages. The first stage (ages 3-7) is considered to be the stage in which the first ideas about the surrounding world and the homeland appear, in which children are taught various poems, tunes and songs, cartoons and various lessons in the family and preschool educational institutions. it involves the formation of love for the motherland based on the understanding of the world through performing games, drawing pictures, getting to know state symbols (flag, coat of arms, anthem).

At this stage, the main attention is paid to:

- telling fairy tales and stories in order to form initial ideas in the direction of patriotism;
- memorizing poems and songs on topics related to love for the motherland, protection of the Motherland is a sacred duty;
- draw pictures to expand children's imagination and organize various contests and contests to strengthen their physical abilities, thereby encouraging them spiritually;
- showing patriotic cartoons and holding various games;
- organizing excursions to military museums and cultural and recreational parks related to the theme of patriotism. In the second stage (ages 7-16), strengthening students' love and loyalty to the Motherland, fulfilling their filial duty to the

motherland with high responsibility, further expanding their positive thoughts towards our Armed Forces, raising the prestige of military service, physically training young people. He is encouraged to do good deeds, such as forming a healthy, spiritually mature, well-rounded, independent-thinking person.

Taking into account the above, it will be appropriate to hold meetings with our young compatriots who have received the "Brave Boy" state award, and to widely promote their achievements and results among young people. "From my own experience, even if the outcome of the case is hidden behind the veil of destiny, it is necessary to seek advice from conscientious and sober people and to know their opinions."

Forming in young people the qualities of an active position and the ability to clearly express their independent opinions, a sense of responsibility, strict order and discipline, and teaching them to be persistent will help achieve the above goals. In the pedagogical analysis and assessment of indicators of the level of patriotism in young people, it is expressed in the careful attitude to the glory, dignity, culture and traditions of the beloved nation. Patriotic citizens are the basis on which the state of Uzbekistan is built. This is what helps to overcome difficulties in the way of re-changing the society, to achieve harmony and cooperation.

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